

Associate Professor of Biostatistics Lindsay D'Amato (she/her)

"I enjoy multidisciplinary collaborative work and the opportunity to learn from a wide variety of scientists with different perspectives."

Bio

Lindsay's lifelong interest in improving people's health and wellbeing led her to the field of biostatistics for her PhD. Working her way up from a junior statistician position wherein she cleaned datasets and performed simple analyses, she is now a direct collaborator with PIs on dozens of grant-funded projects each year. She advises researchers on the appropriate statistical approaches for data analysis plans and plays a key role in study design. Many of Lindsay's projects are multi-center studies, requiring her to travel frequently. She provides mentorship to junior faculty in every stage of the research process, from study design to analysis. Lindsay also advises and mentors graduate-level biostatisticians in her department, helping them along their path of professional development and promotion. Lindsay is grateful for the support of research administration staff and her colleagues in the grant office, who support her project work and assist her as she contributes to grant applications. One challenge Lindsay faces is the lack of an NIH study section to submit to for transdisciplinary grants.

Education: BS, Mathematics; MS, Statistics; PhD, Biostatistics
Years of experience: 10
Work location: Frequent remote work on her laptop

Goals

- Nurture a thriving biostatistics department with team scientist biostatisticians
- Leverage complementary statistical expertise in the department
- Effectively communicate with PIs and project members about expectations
- Gain skills in new statistical programs and methods

Software attitude & use

- Open to new tools
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Box, Trello, GitHub, Slack, Zoom and other video conferencing software
- Specialized resources: frequently used statistical software includes SAS, Stata, PASS, R. Other key resources include REDCap, and funder websites

Outputs

- Articles/manuscripts
- Conference presentations & posters
- Class lectures and materials
- Reviews of others' manuscripts
- Grant application contributor
- Datasets

Pain Points

- Harmonizing data from many different sources requires complicated behind-the-scenes biostatistics solutions
- Working on too many grants at low percent effort leads to distraction, lower commitment, and less satisfaction

Motivators

- Successful grant funding to support both routine and innovative project work, thereby confirming viable research analysis design
- Receive recognition for the vital role biostatisticians play on a wide range of analyses in research
- Report accurate and impactful results
- Conduct accountable, reproducible science that ensures the safety and security of patient data

Wants/Needs

- Formal recognition for collaboration, leadership, and mentorship on team projects
- More time to achieve her goals
- Institutional support for a biostatistics collaboration unit
- A way to track metrics on consulting and collaboration efforts to document productivity
- Clear methodology or algorithm for prioritizing statistical consultation requests
- A way to quickly get help with research and collaboration tools, as problems cause work delays

Professional Development

Department supports travel to conferences and workshops, and purchasing informational resources

Mentors graduate-level biostatisticians

Department encourages biostatisticians to pursue their PhDs

Wants to pursue a professional statistical certification (PStat) from the American Statistical Association